

THE HELPFUL TECHNIQUES TO TEACH VOCABULARY FOR YOUNG LEARNERS

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Abstract: The word reinforcement can be used in relating to the support on building construction or the mechanical structures, however, the word can give us broader meaning as well. In addition, if you say I am going to reinforce the walls, in that case the very word can give us the meaning of “strengthening”. For example, elaborating the notion by asking question in every class also can provide us meaning of reinforcement. In educational field the word reinforcement is mostly used on vocabulary or on reading. Not only the vocabulary that the learners` need can be “taught” learners will need plentiful exposure to talk and text as well as training for self- directed learning.

Key terminology: memorable teaching, word frequency, regency of use, concept mapping, awareness, reinforcing, memory, mental lexicon.

Methodology. While learning new items, learners don`t feel responsibility, and may be unaware of this. Here, it is essential to raise students` awareness about the difficulties of remembering and reminding items and /or words [1]. Teacher can tell and highlight them the following strategies:

- new words should be used both in class for homework and in some other way;
- new words and expressions need to be looking out for while listening and reading activities;
- short stories and paragraphs are written connecting the words and expressions that you want to learn;
- Personalized sentences can be written using the new words relevant to students` life;
- Words need to be kept a small notebook with example sentences. Learners can then take it with them wherever they go and when they have a few minutes.

Another way of reinforcing vocabulary in class successfully is memorable teaching. There are many things we can do to make the learning process more memorable for learners. Using pictures, interesting contexts and stories can help memory and giving the students the opportunity to practice the new vocabulary in personalized and meaningful tasks are also essential tools [5]. The idea is that if the students are asked to analyze and react personally to new information, it will help them to understand more deeply, to keep in their long term memory forever. As

Thornberry states, “To ensure long term recall and retention, new knowledge should be integrated to old existing knowledge, i.e. being compared, combined, matched, sorted, visualized and reshuffled, as well as being repeatedly filed away and recalled [2].

Also it has been suggested that the most two important factors of that affect the keeping the items in a special place for the future use of words are *word frequency* and *regency of use* in the learners` mental lexicon [4].

Although there are many effective strategies for students with altering abilities highlights several strategies. Strategies that yielded positive results include:

- Mnemonics or key word strategy that provide phonetic or imaginary links to target words;
- Direct instruction to word meanings (providing definition, giving synonyms etc);
- Concept enhancement procedures that assist students in making cognitive connections (e.g., semantic or concept mapping) [2].

According to Scott Thornberry, Mnemonics are called as the technique for remembering things. The best mnemonics are followings that:

- have visual elements;
- are self – generated – organized by a learner, not “borrowed from another one.

Scott Thornberry says “The best technique is called the key technique. This involves devising an image that typically connects the pronunciation of the second language word with the meaning of a first language word.” Although devising keywords takes more time, and a certain amount of training, there seems to be no other single technique works as well. Therefore, it is a good idea to allow learners a few minute to select or detect keywords silently and individually, when teaching new learning vocabulary items and words. Then, teacher asks them to share with the partners devised keywords. It will not only reinforce new words, but also it can aid learners to adopt this technique – finding out quickly the most appropriate keywords for the given vocabulary material [2].

The main request to adapt to the technique and have success is to repeat the activity regularly, to carry around with them, until learners get into the habit of obtaining their own.

According David Martin, Learning new words and developing an extended vocabulary, with accompanying compatible definitions, is a common task thought all disciplines and all levels of school. Teachers are always looking for new ways to motivate their students, but when the work is usually dependent on memorization, it often converts into a boring task. Expanding vocabulary is a key element of an English learners overall proficiency with the language [5].

Rolf Palmberg claims that “If the teacher wants to develop in the learners mental lexicons that have a high valence and at the same time practice specific language skills, this can be accomplished using a variety of arranging activities involving the blackboard vocabulary [3].

Conclusion. The technique called “one single keyword” as the starting point, in order to increase learners` word power. This technique can be similar with a technique of the strategy “Using mnemonics” supported by Scott Thornberry. This key word can be any word selected by the teacher or the class. It can be a continuation of something already dealt with or an introduction to a new topic. In this activity the blackboard is the main item, because focused object is blackboard vocabulary.

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